

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF FULL SCALE GRP LAMINATES WITH RANDOMLY DISTRIBUTED FRAGMENT DAMAGES

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1 Introduction

A typical scenario of a naval composite ship hull being exposed to air-borne hostile fire can be described as follows; shortly after detonation a scatter of fragments will travel at high speed creating patterns of penetration and perforation damages on the ship hull. Subsequent to these fragment damages a high intensity pressure wave will cause the ship hull panels to deform at an elevated strain rate. Hence, the high intensity pressure wave hits an already damaged structure motivating the study of notched laminates at high rate loading. The design procedure for handling such a complicated loading scenario could be envisaged by the following steps:

We model the geometry of the blast situation, which could be a compartment or a panel surface. One then places the threat at some position where it explodes. By knowledge of the threat one can simulate each fragment having a particular mass, velocity and direction. Each fragment will thus hit the structure and depending on its mass, incident angle and the structure type (material, thickness, etc.) the fragment will penetrate the structure, create some damage or be completely stopped. One thus follow an arbitrary number of fragments and detect which elements they hit in the structure and if they create some damage (*e.g.* penetration). The next step is to create an FE-mesh of the structure. But from the first step one now reduces the properties of the structure, or structural material, by the amount of damage created by the fragments. Some elements will have many holes and thus considerably lower stiffness and strength than the undamaged material. In the final step one performs the blast analysis by applying a transient shock wave with a given momentum and rise time according to the threat assumed. By adopting such a strategy it should not

be necessary to model each hole or damage in the structure which would lead to enormous amounts of modelling and computational efforts.

The aim of the present paper is to contribute to the second step in the analysis scheme by finding simple and rational methods to predict the strength reduction of composite laminates with stochastic hole patterns generated by *e.g.* fragments. This research is based on a methodology developed by Kazemahvazi and Zenkert [1-3] in which more details on section 2-3 can be found. For this paper the phenomenological residual strength model has been further refined and is now used to predict the strength of full scale composite panels with randomly distributed fragment damages.

2 Experimental protocol – laboratory scale testing

Tri-axial glass fibre non-crimp fabrics infused with vinyl-ester resin have been used for all laboratory scale experiments. The laminates, denoted DBL600, have 33% fibres in the 0-degree direction (loading direction) and remaining fibres in ± 45 degree direction. The specimen dimensions are length x width = 150 mm x 50 mm with a gauge length of 100 mm. A random hole pattern was applied to the central patch of the specimen (50x50 mm). All holes had a diameter of 5 mm. Each specimen was tested in a screw-driven test machine at a quasi-static loading rate. The load was measured using a 30 kN load cell and full strain field measurement was obtained using digital image correlation.

3 Finite Element Analysis

A finite element model was developed in order to make numerical experiments for a number of

different hole configurations and hole densities. The numerical experiments, together with the actual experiments, were used as input for the statistical percolation theory model.

3.1 Model description

The finite element simulations were performed in the commercial finite element code ABAQUS. The specimen was modelled as a shell with composite layup. Constitutive material properties were chosen as in table 1 and calibrated against tensile test experiments for an un-notched specimen. In order to model the onset and progression of damage the in-built damage model for fibre reinforced composite materials was used. This is based on the failure criteria developed by Hashin and Matzenmiller and is described in more detail by Lapczyk and Hurtado [4]. The energy release rates were estimated and calibrated against experimental results for a number of hole configurations – thus the energy release rates were not experimentally measured. Further a small material viscosity, η , was used to improve the convergence of the analysis. In an implicit analysis (quasi-static) the viscosity only have minor effects on the global load-displacement response but improves the convergence rate of the simulation significantly. A discussion on this is given by Lapczyk and Hurtado [4].

A mesh convergence study was performed and an element size of approximate 0.2 mm was required in the vicinity of the hole in order to get sufficiently high resolution of the stress field (and thereby a converged value for the specimen strength).

3.2 Benchmarking of FE-model to experimental data

FE-simulations were benchmarked against experimental observations for a variety of hole densities and hole configurations. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show examples of comparison between FE-simulations and experimental observations. The specimens in these examples have 5 and 10 randomly distributed holes respectively. It is observed that the FE-model is able to predict the global load-deflection response with good accuracy. Comparisons between the full strain fields also show

good agreement both in terms of areas of strain concentrations and the quantitative level of strains.

A summary of all benchmarking FE-simulations are found in table 2. The majority of the simulations show good agreement with the experimental observations. However, hole configurations 5-5 and 10-1 and 20-1 show significantly larger discrepancy. An explanation for this is that each hole configuration was only experimentally tested once. Considering the possibility of small deviations in manufacturing (e.g. in the drilled hole pattern geometry) and the natural deviation in the strength of the material, somewhat larger spread in strength would be expected as compared to un-notched specimens (which usually have a spread of a few percent).

3.3 Residual strength predictions for laminates with large number of randomly distributed holes

The described FE-model was used in order to generate a bulk mass of residual strength data as input for the statistical strength prediction model described in section 4. The benefit of using numerical experiments is that the time consuming process of manufacturing specimens with a large number of holes is reduced. The drawback is however that there will be somewhat larger uncertainties in the input data.

4 Statistical phenomenological model

Percolation theory has been used in order to develop a fast and effective model to predict the residual strength of laminates with randomly distributed holes. The normalized fracture strength, F , as function of hole density, P , can be described by [5-7],

$$F(P) = k \left(\frac{P^c - P}{P^c} \right)^{2.2} \left[1 - m \left(\frac{P^c - P}{P^c} \right) + n \left(\frac{P^c - P}{P^c} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where k , m and n are fitting coefficients. P is the hole density, *i.e.* the total area of holes divided by the total area of the plate. P^c is the percolating threshold. It is defined as the hole density at which the plate will have zero strength. For an infinite plate this value is 0.64 (64 % area of holes). Since the

model is only based on one variable, P , no consideration is taken to changes in residual strength as function of different hole patterns. Further, if the fitting of eq. 1 is performed solely on numerical simulations – potential deviations in residual strength due to deviations in material properties will not be captured.

By assuming that $P^c = 0.64$ and employing a least squares fit based on the Marquardt-Levenberg algorithm the solid line in Fig. 3 is obtained. The fitting coefficients in eq. 1 are then; $k = 1.247$, $m = 1.64$ and $n = 1.185$ resulting in a coefficient of determination of $R^2=0.96$. Fig. 3 now shows the normalized strength as function of the hole density. The squares are data points from experiments and the diamonds are strength predictions by numerical simulations. Although some outliers can be observed the overall accuracy of the fit is good. Obviously, the potential outliers can be identified easier the more experimental and numerical data that is used in the curve fitting model. Thus, the quality of the fit and the accuracy of the strength predictions (eq. 1) will increase with number of observations. Since the present study is only based on a limited number of experiments the quantitative strength predictions will have lower accuracy. Typically hundreds of simulations are required in order to obtain high accuracy fit.

5 Experimental protocol – full scale testing

A total of 14 sandwich panels of dimension 1200 by 800 mm were exposed to real fragments from a fragmenting shell. The panels were placed in a circle around the shell at various distances, see Fig. 4a. The sandwich panels had face sheets made from glass-fibre reinforced composite laminates with DBL-type reinforcement and vinyl-ester matrix.

After being exposed to the fragmenting shells the panels were cut up in their length direction and the face sheets were removed so that each laminate could be tested separately. Tensile testing was performed on laminates of dimension 400 by 1200 mm in the direction of 0-degree fibres. The tests were performed in a MTS universal testing machine at a constant displacement rate of 0.1 mm/s, *i.e.* 6 mm/minute. During the testing the machine displacement and load was monitored. Surface strain

measurements were performed using a digital image correlation system (GOM Aramis). The test set-up is shown in Fig. 4b.

The panel laminates were tested until fracture which in all cases was a net section fracture through some paths along the fragment holes. The failure load was normalised with the cross-section area to calculate a nominal failure stress which was then normalised with the strength of undamaged laminates.

6 Estimation of hole area – full scale testing

From photographs of the panels and also from the strain images from the DIC-measurements one can try to estimate the fraction of holes. Fig. 5-9 shows photographs of panels with fragment holes. These panels represent a side with entry holes, *i.e.* this side was exposed to incoming fragments. The hole radii are still difficult to see clearly. The photographs were read into an imaging software (PAINT.NET), the holes were masked manually and then the photograph was turned into a black-and-white bitmap. The masking was performed using two different techniques, one where only the visible holes were masked (b) and one where the entire delaminated area around the holes were mapped (c). These two masking techniques would represent a lower and an upper bound of the actual hole area of the panels. Each bitmap was analysed with a MatLab-script and the relative area of the holes was calculated.

As can be observed in Fig. 5-9, there is a large spread in the relative hole area depending on what masking techniques that has been used. It was found that the lower masking bounds typically fall in the regime of 8%-10% hole area whereas the upper masking bounds typically fall in the regime of 20% hole area.

7 Comparison between experimental findings, numerical predictions and analytical predictions

As described in section 1, the design procedure for handling a complicated loading scenario as this would be performed by first modelling the fragment scatter produced by a threat (*e.g.* artillery shell). The fragment scatters would give a statistical distribution of amount of holes, hole size and hole position for the loaded panel. This information would then be

used to get the statistical bounds of the residual strength of the fragment damaged panel.

In this paper we are reverse engineering the hole patterns from actual full scale testing which results in an inherent spread of the results correlated to how well the hole areas can be mapped as exemplified in section 6.

The minimum and maximum hole area bounds as function of the normalized residual strength for each panel (panel 1-9) have been plotted in Fig. 3.

In most cases, the percolation theory predictions fall within the area bounds of the full scale experiment panels. There are, however, a number of observations to be made.

All panels have a span in area bound of approximately 10 percent points except for panel 3. Looking at the hole patterns for panel 3 (Fig. 6a), it can be seen that there are a high number of small holes (approximately 40 holes) and around each hole a significant delamination area is observed. These delamination areas add up to a larger total area resulting in a high upper bound. In reality, the amount of holes in the panel is likely closer to the lower bound which is also in agreement with the analytical predictions.

The residual strength for two panels, P7 and P5, falls outside of the analytical predicted value. P7 has somewhat higher residual strength than the analytical predictions and P5 has somewhat lower residual strength than the analytical predictions.

Looking at panel 5 (Fig. 7a), a large damage zone can be observed over the mid-section of the panel. A crack like formation runs from left edge of the panel to the right edge. A concentrated damage zone like this can explain why the residual strength of the panel is low despite a small area of damage.

Looking at panel 7 (Fig. 9a), the damages look quite the opposite. There are a large number of holes (resulting in large hole area) but the holes are well distributed with little damage between the holes. Portions of the panel have almost no damage (on contrary to panel 5) and are able to carry and distribute the load between the holes resulting in higher residual strength.

8 Concluding remarks

The scenario of coupled fragment and blast loading has been investigated by analysing the residual strength of panels with multiple holes and fragment damages. A time-efficient semi-analytical model, based on percolation theory, has been developed to predict the residual strength of panel with a predefined damage/hole area. In order to calibrate the percolation theory model, laboratory scale experiments has been performed on specimens with a range of randomly distributed hole patterns. To build a larger base of statistical data, a finite element model was developed and used to perform numerical experiments on a larger set of different hole patterns. Finally, a limited number of full scale experiments have been performed on composite panels which have been subjected to fragment impacts from a real blast scenario. It is concluded that the analytical model, albeit being based on only a single variable (hole area), is useful to predict the residual strength of panels with randomly distributed fragment damages.

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E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	$\hat{\sigma}_{1t}$ (MPa)	$\hat{\sigma}_{1c}$ (MPa)	$\hat{\sigma}_{2t}$ (MPa)	$\hat{\sigma}_{2c}$ (MPa)	$\hat{\tau}_{12}$ (MPa)
41	9.8	2.8	1250	600	20	100	60
<hr/>							
X_{1t} (N/mm)	X_{1c} (N/mm)	X_{2t} (N/mm)	X_{2c} (N/mm)	η			
15	15	0.5	0.5	< 0.0005			

Table 1: Material data properties used in the finite element model. The indexes 1 and 2 refer to the axes along and transverse the fibre direction respectively. The indexes t and c refer to tensile and compressive loading. E is the Young’s modulus, G the shear modulus, σ the strength, X the energy release rate and η the viscosity coefficient.

Specimen	Failure load Exp. (kN)	Failure load FE (kN)	Discrepancy
5-1	9.13	8.70	-4.7%
5-2	8.14	7.43	-8.7%
5-3	8.53	8.05	-5.7%
5-4	8.68	8.97	3.3%
5-5	10.09	7.40	-26.7%
10-1	11.32	8.82	-22.1%
10-2	8.31	8.18	-1.5%
10-3	8.99	9.24	2.7%
10-4	7.86	7.15	-9.0%
10-5	7.95	7.97	0.2%
20-1	5.82	7.38	26.8%
20-2	5.77	6.15	6.6%
20-3	8.15	8.07	-1.0%

Table 2: Summary of simulations benchmarked against experimentally measured failure load.

Fig.1. Comparison between experimental and FEA load-deflection curve for a specimen with 10 randomly distributed holes.

Fig.2. Comparison between experimental and FEA load-deflection curve for a specimen with 5 randomly distributed holes.

Fig. 3. Summary of laboratory experiments (squares), numerical predictions (diamonds) and large scale experiments (crosses).

Fig. 4. (a) Set-up for fragmentation and (b) set-up for tensile testing of damaged panels.

Fig. 5. Graphs of Panel 1 (P1); (a) Pre tensile test photograph (b) Minimum masking around holes only (c) Maximum masking including all delamination (d) Digital Image Correlation graph at peak load

Fig. 6. Graphs of Panel 3 (P3); (a) Pre tensile test photograph (b) Minimum masking around holes only (c) Maximum masking including all delamination

Fig. 7. Graphs of Panel 5 (P5); (a) Pre tensile test photograph (b) Minimum masking around holes only (c) Maximum masking including all delamination

Fig. 8. Graphs of Panel 6 (P6); (a) Pre tensile test photograph (b) Minimum masking around holes only (c) Maximum masking including all delamination

Fig. 9. Graphs of Panel 7 (P7); (a) Pre tensile test photograph (b) Minimum masking around holes only (c) Maximum masking including all delamination